

Temporal Augmentation for Remote AV Takeover: A Dual-Phase Evaluation of Replay-Buffered Interfaces

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Figure 1: Symmetric dual-phase validation framework. Both evaluation paths follow identical analytical stages. Upper path (User Study): Behavioral measurements feed into Bayesian ANOVA, revealing scenario effects ($BF > 18$) but no GUI effects ($BF < 0.5$), consistent with limited timeline engagement and perceived attentional trade-offs. Lower path (Simulation-Based Screening): Saliency measurements feed into classification models, achieving high discrimination accuracy (94.7%), confirming structural GUI divergence. The symmetric analysis highlights a dissociation pattern: simulation-based screening detects bottom-up differences that do not manifest as experiential effects in human operators.

Abstract

Remote teleoperation is critical for handling edge cases in autonomous vehicle operations, yet current Takeover Request interfaces often lack retrospective context, impairing operators' ability to rapidly build situation awareness. We developed two graphical user interfaces, a live-view "Actual Interface" and a "Buffered Interface" augmented with a scrub-able replay timeline, and evaluated them through a dual-phase methodology combining simulation-based saliency analysis with a within-subject user study and post-task interviews. Saliency classifiers confirmed that the interfaces are structurally distinguishable in their bottom-up attentional properties. However, Bayesian repeated-measures analysis revealed that scenario complexity, rather than interface condition, dominated variance in cognitive workload, situation awareness, and takeover time. Qualitative data clarified this pattern: participants rarely engaged with the timeline, perceiving the attentional cost of reviewing past frames as prohibitive under time pressure. Our findings advocate for multi-layer evaluation combining computational screening with human-in-the-loop

testing and qualitative inquiry to guide Takeover Request interface design.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **User studies; Empirical studies in HCI; User interface design;** • **Computing methodologies** → *Cognitive science.*

Keywords

Autonomous Vehicles, Remote Teleoperation, Takeover Request, Situation Awareness, Cognitive Workload, Temporal Visualization, Visual Attention, Interface Evaluation

ACM Reference Format:

Gerhard Graf. 2026. Temporal Augmentation for Remote AV Takeover: A Dual-Phase Evaluation of Replay-Buffered Interfaces. In *Proceedings of the 2026 International Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces (AVI '26)*, June 08–12, 2026, Venice, Italy. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 7 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3811427.3811435>

1 Introduction

Commercial large-scale deployment of ride-hailing fleets of Autonomous Vehicle (AV) still requires timely human intervention in edge-case situations that may arise due to, for example, broken infrastructure, ambiguous or absent traffic controls, unexpected

obstacles, or ad-hoc police directions. Vehicle teleoperation, that is the remote supervision and control of an AV by an off-board operator, has therefore emerged as a critical socio-technical layer for maintaining safety, service continuity, and public trust in automated mobility ecosystems. Designing interfaces that restore Situation Awareness (SA) swiftly and reliably is thus crucial for the viability of commercial AV services.

While implementations differ, many current teleoperation workstations still rely primarily on real-time video streams along with conventional control devices. Retrospective sensor context or enriched situational cues are often limited or absent. When a Take-over Request (ToR) is issued, the operator, lacking embodied cues such as vestibular feedback, peripheral vision, and ambient sound, must re-establish SA under severe time pressure. Unlike a co-located driver, the remote operator cannot draw on proprioceptive or haptic signals to gauge vehicle dynamics, nor on the multimodal environmental context that supports rapid orientation in conventional driving. Temporal augmentation (specifically, access to a short replay buffer) offers a partial compensatory mechanism: by externalising recently elapsed sensor states, it provides an explicit perceptual record that can substitute for the continuous, embodied situational context otherwise unavailable remotely. Addressing this shortfall motivates the work presented in this paper.

We developed two functionally equivalent Graphical User Interface (GUI) that differ only in temporal augmentation: an *Actual Interface* that streams a strictly live view, and a *Buffered Interface* that includes a fifteen-second scrub-able timeline. The interfaces were evaluated through a dual-phase methodology: (1) a simulation-based screening using DeepGaze III saliency models to assess whether the interfaces exhibit distinguishable bottom-up attentional structure, and (2) a controlled within-subject laboratory study involving eighteen participants. Key outcome measures included Takeover Time (ToT), SA assessed via the Situation Awareness Rating Technique (SART), and perceived cognitive workload via the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX).

Simulation results confirmed that the two interfaces are structurally distinguishable (classification accuracy = 94.7%). However, Bayesian repeated-measures Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) favored models excluding GUI effects, with scenario complexity (not GUI condition) dominating variance. Post-task interviews clarified this pattern: participants perceived the attentional cost of switching to the replay as prohibitive, resulting in minimal timeline use. In this laboratory decision-assessment setting, no reliable GUI effect was observed. Our findings advocate combining saliency simulation with human-in-the-loop testing and interaction telemetry to guide ToR interface design. In summary, our work contributes:

- (1) **Temporal-Augmented ToR Interface Design:** We present the design and implementation of a buffered replay interface for remote AV takeover, grounded in Endsley’s SA model and Cognitive Load Theory.
- (2) **Dual-Phase Evaluation Framework:** We introduce a methodology that combines computational screening (DeepGaze III saliency analysis) with empirical validation (Bayesian inference on human-subject data), demonstrating

how these layers can yield complementary, and at times divergent, insights.

- (3) **Empirical Evidence for Design Guidance:** In this laboratory decision-assessment setting, we observed no reliable effect of a 15-second replay buffer on operator performance; post-task interviews indicated that the perceived attentional cost of retrospective review discouraged active timeline use.

2 Background and Related Work

In a teleoperation setting, the operator observes the remote environment through audio-visual feeds and issues control commands via familiar input devices (e.g., steering wheel, pedals, or haptic joysticks). The operator effectively closes the feedback loop that the automated system cannot resolve, stabilizing the vehicle during challenging manoeuvres [2, 18]. Although driver-assist functions (such as lane-keeping or obstacle detection) can remain active, the operator is ultimately responsible for interpreting the scene and executing the manoeuvre. The separation between physical presence (the operator being outside the vehicle) and control authority (the ability to override automation) results in coordination challenges that are absent in conventional, co-located driving scenarios.

The Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and automotive safety literature on human-automation collaboration offers relevant insights, especially the extensive body of work on ToR. A ToR is issued when an AV approaches or exceeds its operational design domain and requires a human to resume control [7, 8]. Existing studies, however, assume that the driver is physically co-located with the vehicle, and therefore focus on gaze re-engagement, in-cabin controls, and proprioceptive feedback. Remote teleoperation violates this assumption: the operator has no access to vestibular and vibrotactile cues, and may lack knowledge of the vehicle’s recent operational history or the reason for the ToR. While cognitive load and decision-making demands may transfer between settings, the absence of embodied cues may impair SA unless specifically compensated for through interface design.

One promising approach is the use of temporal visualizations (interactive timelines, video scrubbing, and replay buffers) to reconstruct recent events after an interruption. In the robotics domain, Sellner et al. [17] showed that replaying 5–10s of buffered multi-camera video enables operators to regain SA more quickly and reduces control errors during the autonomy-to-teleoperation hand-over. Similarly, Chang et al. [1] demonstrated that interactive timelines on a shared tabletop improve team SA in collaborative analytic tasks, while Nunes et al. [14] employed temporally compressed “video slices” to let distributed users review changes in a media space. Across these studies, temporal visualizations supply structured external cues that allow operators to orient themselves in dynamic, information-dense environments.

Building on this work, we present a dual-phase evaluation of a ToR GUI for remote AV teleoperation, combining computational saliency screening with a controlled user study. Our study investigates (i) the impact of a buffered replay timeline on operator SA and cognitive workload, and (ii) the conditions under which

temporal augmentation may, or may not, yield experiential benefits.

3 Interface Design

To isolate the effect of temporal augmentation, we designed two interface variants with identical spatial layout and control affordances. Both display an upper strip with three video panes (front camera with semantic overlays, flanked by placeholders for rear cameras), a main viewport showing a top-down LiDAR scene with trajectory and bounding boxes, and a takeover button in the lower-right corner.

The *Actual Interface* presents a strictly live feed. The *Buffered Interface* adds a scrub-able timeline along the bottom edge, enabling operators to review the preceding 15 seconds without altering control affordances. This augmentation enriches epistemic access while preserving the semantics of the takeover action.

3.1 Theoretical Grounding and Design Hypotheses

The design of the Buffered Interface is motivated by two complementary theoretical frameworks: Endsley’s model of SA [6] and Cognitive Load Theory [19]. Regarding SA, the timeline targets all three levels: it sustains perceptual continuity (Level 1) by keeping recent sensor states accessible [5], supports comprehension (Level 2) by enabling reconstruction of causal chains without relying on internal recall, and facilitates projection (Level 3) through access to event history for trend extrapolation. From the Cognitive Load Theory perspective, the timeline functions as an external memory aid: intrinsic load remains unchanged (the core task is identical), and germane load may benefit from externalised sequence reconstruction. The timeline does introduce additional visual structure and potential attentional switching costs; however, we hypothesize that this does not translate into reliably higher perceived workload. These theoretical considerations yield three testable predictions:

- H1** *No workload penalty*: The Buffered condition will not reliably increase NASA-TLX scores.
- H2** *No SA degradation*: The Buffered condition will not reliably decrease SART scores.
- H3** *No response time cost*: The Buffered condition will not reliably increase ToT.

The simulation study tests whether the interfaces are structurally distinguishable (a prerequisite for meaningful comparison); the user study tests whether this structural difference translates into experiential differences as predicted by H1–H3. While the theoretical grounding targets Endsley’s three-level SA model, our operationalization focuses on *perceived* SA via self-report (SART) rather than objective recall-based freeze-probe measures. This choice aligns with the decision-assessment design, where participants evaluate readiness to intervene rather than execute control maneuvers.

4 Simulation-Based Screening

Prior to laboratory evaluation, we employed DeepGaze III [12] as a computational screening tool to assess whether the two interface

variants exhibit distinguishable bottom-up attentional structure. This simulation phase was not intended to predict user behavior, but to establish that the GUI designs differ in ways detectable by low-level visual processing, thereby motivating empirical validation.

DeepGaze III is a deep neural network trained on large-scale eye-tracking corpora, achieving state-of-the-art saliency prediction on natural scenes (MIT1003: AUC-Judd = 0.916). While its applicability to GUI stimuli is limited—task-driven attention and semantic knowledge are not modeled, the tool provides a cost-effective proxy for identifying structural visual differences prior to user testing, consistent with lightweight pre-evaluation principles [15].

Synthetic scanpaths were generated using empirically grounded parameters: 10 fixations per path (matching MIT1003 mean scanpath length [11]), a 10×10 spatial grid for saliency pooling [21], and log-normal fixation durations ($\mu = \ln 180$ ms, $\sigma = 0.35$) reflecting GUI viewing patterns [20]. Decision-tree classifiers trained on these synthetic data reliably discriminated the Actual from the Buffered interface at both fixation-level (accuracy = 0.875) and scanpath-level (accuracy = 0.947), confirming measurable structural divergence.

This computational discriminability does not entail experiential differences for users; the simulation serves only to establish that the temporal augmentation introduces visual complexity detectable by bottom-up mechanisms, whether this complexity translates into cognitive burden is an empirical question addressed in the user study.

5 User Study Design

We conducted a within-subject experiment to test hypotheses H1–H3, examining how the *Actual Interface* and *Buffered Interface* influence operators’ cognitive load, SA, and response time during remote takeovers. Each participant completed two trials, experiencing each GUI variant once and each scenario once, with the GUI–Scenario pairing counterbalanced across participants [3]. This design ensures that both factors are fully crossed at the group level while controlling for order effects.

5.1 Scenarios

Two urban scenarios were developed in CAR Learning to Act [4], both depicting obstacle-avoidance situations inspired by National Highway Traffic Safety Administration pre-crash typology [13]. In both cases, the ego vehicle encountered an unexpected stationary obstacle requiring a double lane-change maneuver [10]. The AV trajectory indicated straight travel until obstacle detection triggered the ToR. Participants were not required to execute the maneuver but to assess the situation prompting the takeover request. This deliberate design choice isolates the cognitive assessment phase from motor execution demands, aligning with teleoperation research that separates readiness-to-intervene judgments from vehicle control [18]. Because the study targets the *comprehension* stage of Endsley’s SA model, where the replay buffer is theoretically most relevant, performance-oriented measures (e.g., manoeuvre accuracy, lane deviation, or collision avoidance) were not included. Future work should extend the paradigm to closed-loop execution tasks so that the relationship

Figure 2: Structural comparison of the Actual Interface (left column) and Buffered Interface (right column). Top row: Full-resolution interface screenshots showing the front-camera view, top-down LiDAR scene with bounding-box annotations, and the takeover button. The Buffered Interface (top right) includes a 15-second scrub-able timeline along the bottom edge, enabling retrospective navigation while preserving the same control affordances. Bottom row: Simulated attention distribution generated by DeepGaze III, overlaid with predicted scanpaths (numbered fixation sequence). Warmer colors indicate higher predicted saliency. The temporal augmentation introduces systematic differences in bottom-up attentional structure, as validated by decision-tree classification (accuracy = 94.7%).

between temporal augmentation and control performance can be evaluated directly.

5.2 Measures

For each trial we collected three outcome measures. Subjective workload was assessed immediately post-trial using the raw NASA-TLX [9]. SA was captured via the Situation Awareness Rating Technique (SART) [16], a self-report instrument assessing perceived attentional demand, supply, and understanding. Finally, Takeover Time (ToT), the elapsed time between scene onset and button press, was logged automatically by the experimental software. Each participant thus contributed two observations per measure.

5.3 Participants and Procedure

Eighteen participants (5 female, 13 male; $M_{age} = 32.0$ years, $SD = 9.6$, range = 24–68) were recruited via convenience sampling through mailing lists and personal networks. Sixteen held a valid driver’s license ($M = 13.0$ years, $SD = 10.7$). Fifteen had prior

experience with remote-controlled devices (e.g., drones). None had prior experience with AV teleoperation. The experimental workstation consisted of a Microsoft Surface Studio 2 (28-inch touchscreen, 4500×3000 px) with GUIs developed in HTML5/CSS3 and rendered full-screen. Upon arrival, participants provided informed consent, completed a demographic questionnaire, and received a demonstration followed by a practice scenario. Each participant then completed two experimental trials in counterbalanced order, one per GUI variant, pressing the takeover button once they felt adequately informed. The NASA-TLX and SART were administered immediately after each trial.

To complement quantitative measures, we conducted brief post-task stimulated recall interviews with all participants immediately after the experimental trials (≈20 minutes, max. 25 minutes). Following a structured interview guide, we replayed key task moments (around the ToR decision) and asked participants to articulate (i) what they were trying to understand, (ii) whether and why they engaged with the replay timeline (or chose not to), and (iii) perceived trade-offs between retrospective review and

real-time monitoring. Interviews were audio-recorded and anonymized. We analyzed the material using a lightweight thematic coding approach with a hybrid deductive–inductive scheme (e.g., engagement vs. non-engagement, usage triggers, perceived barriers, and decision strategies) to derive recurrent patterns used to interpret the quantitative outcomes. One researcher coded all interviews; a second reviewed the codebook and a subset of coded excerpts. In addition, participants provided a perceived-utility rating of the timeline on a 0–3 scale.

6 Results

Preliminary descriptive analyses indicated that all measures exhibited acceptable distributional properties. Skewness and kurtosis values remained within conventional thresholds ($|2|$), and no violations of normality were detected based on the Shapiro-Wilk test (all p -values $> .05$), with the exception of the ToT scores, which were subsequently log-transformed to improve distributional symmetry. Although two univariate outliers were observed in the NASA-TLX measures, their influence was limited and did not warrant exclusion. The decision to retain all observations was supported by the robustness of Bayesian statistical inference to mild deviations from normality.

Bayesian repeated-measures ANOVA was conducted for each dependent variable with GUI and Scenario as within-subject factors. All models included participant as a random effect. Descriptive statistics by GUI condition (collapsed across scenarios) are summarised in Table 1.

For all three measures, the Scenario-only model received the highest posterior probability: NASA-TLX, $P(M|data) = .654$; ToT (log-transformed), $.637$; SART, $.568$. Scenario exerted a robust influence on all measures, with inclusion Bayes Factors of $BF_{incl} = 149.5$ (NASA-TLX), 18.5 (ToT), and 588.8 (SART). Urban B elicited higher workload and longer ToT than Urban A. In contrast, evidence favored *exclusion* of both the GUI main effect ($BF_{incl} = 0.35–0.51$) and the GUI \times Scenario interaction ($BF_{incl} = 0.56–0.76$), indicating that the data are approximately twice as likely under models omitting GUI effects. Note that the design is primarily powered to test main effects (each participant experienced each GUI and each scenario once); interaction evidence should therefore be interpreted cautiously.

Evidence favored models excluding GUI main effects, suggesting that, across the two tested scenarios, temporal augmentation did not measurably affect operator performance.

To contextualise these values: mean ToT was approximately 52–59 seconds across conditions, substantially longer than the 5–15 second takeover times typically reported in co-located ToR studies [7, 8]. This difference likely reflects the decision-assessment nature of the task: participants were instructed to press the button only once they felt adequately informed, rather than to respond as quickly as possible. The absence of embodied cues that support rapid orientation in conventional driving may also contribute. Whether these response times would be acceptable under operational time constraints remains an open question for future time-critical task designs.

NASA-TLX scores in both conditions ($M \approx 45$) correspond to moderate perceived workload, comparable to values reported for

supervisory control tasks in the human factors literature [9]. SART scores ($M \approx 59$) indicate moderate perceived SA, consistent with the relatively manageable complexity of single-vehicle, single-obstacle scenarios under ideal conditions. The near-identical values across GUI conditions reinforce the Bayesian evidence for practical equivalence.

6.1 Qualitative Findings

Post-task interviews clarified the mechanism underlying the null quantitative effects. A consistent finding was the *conditional utility* of the timeline buffer: while all participants acknowledged its potential value, actual usage was constrained by a perceived attentional trade-off. P01 articulated this tension: “while I look at the past, the present continues—in a dynamic context, losing even 2–3 seconds of awareness can be critical.”

Participants reported that timeline engagement was triggered primarily by (1) oclusions, where actors appeared without apparent origin; (2) causal ambiguity, when system warnings lacked transparent justification; and (3) rapid multi-actor events exceeding real-time comprehension. Conversely, participants avoided the timeline when scenes were sufficiently “readable” from current state alone or when time pressure felt prohibitive.

Quantitative utility ratings (0–3 scale) revealed modest perceived value ($M = 1.25$, range: 1–2), suggesting the timeline functioned more as a “cognitive safety net” (providing psychological reassurance) than as an actively utilized tool. As P06 noted: “I knew it was there, but the attentional cost of using it often exceeded the perceived benefit.” These findings suggest the null quantitative effects reflect *limited engagement* rather than top-down compensation for additional complexity.

7 Discussion

The results reveal a dissociation between computational and experiential evaluation layers: structurally distinguishable interfaces produced no measurable differences in operator experience. This section examines why, and what this implies for evaluation methodology and practice.

7.1 Interpreting the Null Effect

The absence of a reliable GUI effect warrants careful interpretation. Three complementary explanations emerge from the combined quantitative and qualitative data. First, the *limited engagement* account: interview data consistently indicated that participants chose not to use the timeline in most trials, perceiving the attentional cost of shifting from the live feed as too high given the time pressure. When a tool is not actively used, it cannot be expected to produce measurable effects on workload or SA. Second, the *scenario simplicity* account: both scenarios featured a single stationary obstacle in an otherwise readable scene, potentially placing a ceiling on the benefit of retrospective review. More complex, multi-actor scenarios with higher causal ambiguity may elicit greater timeline engagement, a prediction directly supported by participants’ self-reported triggers for timeline use. Third, the *task design* account: because participants assessed readiness rather than executing control manoeuvres, the decision

		95% Confidence Interval Mean			Std. Deviation	MAD	IQR	Minimum	Maximum
		Mean	Lower	Upper					
NASA TLX	Actual	45.28	37.68	52.88	15.28	9.17	12.50	15.00	66.67
	Buffered	44.63	37.45	51.81	14.44	11.67	22.08	20.00	65.00
SART	Actual	58.29	50.24	66.34	16.19	9.53	18.25	34.92	93.65
	Buffered	60.14	52.06	68.22	16.25	8.73	18.66	38.10	92.06
ToT (s)	Actual	52.49	38.62	66.36	27.89	20.52	48.00	20.63	105.05
	Buffered	59.12	31.42	86.82	55.71	22.07	54.56	12.13	199.87

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics by GUI Condition

process may have been dominated by spatial comprehension of the current scene, for which the live feed alone was sufficient.

The study did not include objective performance measures such as decision accuracy or safety-relevant outcomes (e.g., collision avoidance, lane deviation). The rationale was to isolate the *cognitive assessment* phase from motor execution demands; however, this limits the interpretability of the null finding. It remains possible that the replay buffer would yield measurable benefits in closed-loop scenarios where operators must execute manoeuvres and where retrospective context could improve decision quality. Future studies should incorporate both cognitive and performance-based dependent variables.

7.2 Implications

The dual-phase evaluation framework demonstrates how simulation-based screening and human-in-the-loop testing can be productively combined. Saliency modeling confirmed structural differences in bottom-up attentional properties, while the user study revealed that such differences do not automatically translate into experiential burden. Interface evaluations relying solely on computational metrics risk overestimating cognitive costs; conversely, bypassing simulation may leave designers unaware of latent complexity.

The strong scenario effect ($BF_{incl} > 18$) confirms that operational context dominates variance, underscoring the importance of scenario diversity in future evaluations. The wide range of ToT values (12–200 seconds) further suggests substantial inter-individual variability in assessment strategies, which should be explored through larger and more diverse samples.

From a practitioner perspective, these results provide preliminary support, within the bounds of the tested conditions, for deploying short replay buffers without incurring measurable workload penalties. However, this conclusion is limited by the absence of performance-oriented measures and closed-loop control tasks. Future deployments should incorporate interaction telemetry (e.g., scrubbing frequency, dwell time on buffered frames) to quantify usage patterns objectively and determine whether the buffer yields tangible benefits under more demanding conditions. Regarding regulation, teleoperation is increasingly recognised as a transitional mechanism toward higher-level autonomy, and our findings supply initial empirical input for frameworks such as Germany’s draft *Straßenverkehr-Fernlenkverordnung*: the presence of a 15-second replay buffer does not compromise time-critical decision making

under the conditions tested, though its *utility* when actively used remains to be established.

7.3 Limitations

Several constraints bound the generalisability of these findings. First, participants assessed readiness to intervene but did not execute the takeover manoeuvre, and no objective performance metrics (e.g., decision accuracy, collision rates) were collected. While this design intentionally isolates cognitive assessment from motor execution, it lowers ecological validity and limits the ability to determine whether the replay buffer improves the *quality* of takeover decisions. Timeline engagement was assessed exclusively through post-task self-report; without interaction telemetry or eye-tracking, conclusions about usage depth rest on retrospective accounts subject to recall bias. Future studies should incorporate closed-loop execution tasks, performance-based dependent variables, and objective interaction logging.

Second, only two urban obstacle-avoidance scenarios were tested under ideal network conditions, with a single stationary obstacle and a fixed 15-second buffer length. No adverse events (e.g., packet loss, multi-hazard environments) were modelled. Qualitative data suggest that timeline utility is situation-dependent; more complex scenarios and adaptive buffer horizons may elicit different engagement patterns.

Third, the convenience-recruited sample ($N = 18$) and laboratory-grade single-vehicle setup diverge from operational fleet-control rooms with concurrent multi-vehicle supervision. Larger and more diverse samples, including professional teleoperators, are needed to assess generalisability.

8 Conclusion

In a laboratory decision-assessment setting, a 15-second replay buffer did not reliably affect cognitive load, situation awareness, or takeover time. Qualitative data attribute this to low timeline engagement rather than insensitive instrumentation. The dissociation between computational discriminability and experiential equivalence underscores the need for multi-layer validation combining simulation, human-in-the-loop testing, and interaction telemetry. Future work should prioritise objective interaction logging, extend testing to closed-loop execution tasks and multi-vehicle fleet contexts, explore adaptive buffer lengths, and include performance-based outcome measures alongside cognitive assessments.

Data Availability Statement

The dataset supporting this analysis is available in the Open Science Framework repository ¹. The complete analysis is provided as supplementary material, enabling full reproducibility.

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¹<https://osf.io/v7jfs>